

Decentralization and control of corruption in Chile: Alternatives for accountable autonomy in local governments

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Abstract

The decentralization of the subnational government level has been one of the main debates in Chile in the past twenty years. Nevertheless, only modest progress has been achieved in this direction, and Chile still remains among the most centralized countries in the OECD. This paper explores different alternatives for fiscal decentralization in municipalities, particularly with regard to its possible effects on corruption and control of corruption at the local level. The literature is inconclusive about the linkages between decentralization and corruption, and it underscores the relevance of institutional and socioeconomic contextual factors. Building on Mungiu-Pippidi's equilibrium model, this paper assesses the current balance between resources and constraints for corruption in Chilean municipalities. With this assessment as a basis, it compares risks and advantages of mechanisms of symmetric and asymmetric fiscal decentralization. The paper recommends a process of asymmetric decentralization, taking into particular consideration the significant economic and social differences between municipalities in Chile

Keywords

decentralization; constitutional reform; local government; fiscal policy; Chile

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Introduction

The Chilean government has made decentralization a priority since the late 2000's (OECD, 2017). Currently, a transversal political consensus exists in the country about the necessity to advance in a decentralization process that reverts at some degree the significant political and administrative centralization that characterizes the Chilean State. Now, any important modification of the distribution of competences between level of governments, especially if this redistribution has a financial nature, requires the implementation or the strengthening of mechanisms guaranteeing the fair and transparent administration of new sources of revenue.

Building on Mungiu-Pippidi's equilibrium model, this paper explores different decentralization schemes and their capacity to maintain an adequate balance between resources and constraints for corruption, in terms that, if a larger financial autonomy to local governments (municipalities) is granted, it could be compensated with different and adequate types of accountability and transparency mechanisms. Particularly, two different alternatives are assessed. First, a symmetric fiscal decentralization measure by which uniform new financial competences as well as monitor and accountability mechanisms are allocated to all local governments. Second, an asymmetric fiscal decentralization measure by which an incremental process of allocation of new competences is implemented following a pre-defined criteria and the previous assessment of local needs and capacities. A recommendation is made suggesting a process of asymmetric decentralization, taking into consideration, particularly, the significant disparities between municipalities in Chile in terms of socioeconomic context and capacities.

This paper is structured as a policy analysis. First, it describes the discussion regarding different corruption explanatory models and proposes the theoretical framework used for the subsequent analysis. Second, it states the analysis problem and its methodology. Third, based on Mungiu-Pippidi's equilibrium model, it assesses the main characteristics of Chile's subnational governance, particularly with regard to resources and constraints for corruption at the municipal level. Fourth and final, it suggests the components of two different alternatives for fiscal decentralization in municipalities and proposes a recommendation, arguing the adequacy of an asymmetrical fiscal decentralization process for municipalities in Chile.

Theoretical framework

Corruption may be defined in simple terms as "the abuse of entrusted power for private gain" (Transparency International, 2009). On the other hand, this broad definition could entail a wide range of activities, so conceptual distinctions between different forms and purposes of this "abuse" need to be taken into consideration if competent countermeasures are going to be defined (CoR, 2018).

Moreover, general explanatory models of corruption have been developed with the goal of contributing to our understating of corruption. Currently, the most prominent of these models is the principal-agent theory applied to corruption research, attributed originally to the work of Rose-Ackermann (1978) and later developed by Klitgaard (1988). This approach revolves around the relationship between principal and agent, characterized by a divergence of interests, an asymmetry of information to the advantage of the agent, but also by the capacity of the principal to prescribe pay-off rules in their relation (Groenendijk, 1997). Corruption then arises when the principal, due to information asymmetry, lacks the capacity to fully monitor the actions of the agent, providing the latter with more discretion to pursue his or her own self-interest at the expense of the interest of the principal (Mungiu-Pippidi & Hartmann, 2019). Building on Gary Becker's principle of deterrence (1968), the theorem proposes that an agent, on the basis of a rational-choice, will only decide to engage in

corruption if the expected net benefits outweigh the net costs, which in this case depends primarily on the probability of getting caught and penalized (Mungiu-Pippidi & Hartmann, 2019). As indicated by Walton and Jones, this approach has been widely adopted by the anti-corruption agenda steered by organizations such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the United Nations (2017).

Regardless of its influence, the principal-agent model has also been subjected to criticism. Primarily, some scholars have pointed out its lack of adequacy for contexts in which corruption is not an exception capable of be addressed from the point of view of the principal-agent approach, but a systemic feature of society. This could be the case of developing countries with weak bureaucracies but strong communal ties, in which corruption can be recognized as the norm (Persson, Rothstein, & Teorell, 2013). In these cases, a turn to a more systemic approach such as Elinor's Ostrom collective action theory is proposed: where corruption is systematic a social dilemma arises, for which citizens engage in corruption behavior even though they understand its harmful collective consequences, as they find no incentives to not conform to a practice that is rather see as common practice or institution (Ostrom, 1990; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2011; Walton, 2017).

Nevertheless, these criticisms, the principal-agent model continues to be very influential among scholars and international organizations, and still can offer useful conceptual tools to approach corruption in determined contexts, particularly where corruption can still be understood as an exception. As Mungiu-Pippidi puts it, "in short, principal-agent models are a better fit for developed and modern contexts, which have already reached rule of law and enjoy autonomous bureaucracies, appointed by merit and tenured, and do not fit developing or simply poor countries" (Mungiu-Pippidi & Hartmann, 2019: 13). On the contrary, in contexts where corruption is the norm and where the integrity of the principal can no longer be assumed, a collective action model must be preferred.

Reached this point, is then relevant to define the model that most fit the particular characteristic of the society that is the object of this study, in this case Chile. For this purpose, different measures can be employed with the goal of conducting a general assessment of how close Chilean society is to one of the divergent ideal types described above.

Regarding the prevalence of corruption in the country, both subjective and objective measures can be used. In the case of subjective measurements, particularly perception of corruption indicators, Chile has systematically enjoyed an exceptional position, for regional standards. Regarding the Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), in its 2020 version, Chile scored 67 points out of 100², and ranked 25 out 180 countries. These results position the country highly above the world average (43/100), and also the regional average (also 43/100), with only Canada (77/100) and Uruguay (71) outperforming the country in the Americas (United States received also a score of 67/100). These results can also be reflected in the World Bank Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI). Its Control of Corruption (CoC) indicator measures the perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as "capture" of the state by elites and private interests. In this index Chile's 2020 percentile rank is 84.14, which positions the country highly above the Latin America & Caribbean median (50.99).

In the case of objective measurements, several observable indicators to monitor corruption in Chile can be used. The Index of Public Integrity (IPI) assesses the capacity of society to control corruption and ensure that public resources are spent without corrupt practices. It is focused in six components: judicial independence, administrative burden, trade openness, budget transparency, e-

² CPI uses a scale from 0 to 100, in which 100 is very clean and 0 highly corrupt.

citizenship, and freedom of the press. According to this index creators, “these factors are supposed to reflect the complex mechanisms between transparency and accountability on one side and limited resources for discretionary power on the other, in order to establish a national framework for public integrity” (Mungiu-Pippidi and Dadašov, 2016). According to data released in 2021, when compared to its peers in Latin America, Chile ranks among the best performers in the region with 7.49/10 points, lagging only behind Uruguay and Costa Rica, with 7.88 and 8.12 points, respectively.

Now, particularly important for the objective of this assessment is the judicial independence indicator, for its relation to the rule of law. This IPI component captures the extent to which the judiciary system in the country is impartial and non-corrupt in terms of constituting a legal constraint on government power. On 2021 Chile has a score of 7.33/10 and is placed in the second position at regional level, behind Uruguay. This can be explained by the fact that the country has enjoyed a long history of constitutional and democratic rule, in which the law served as the source of governmental legitimacy (Hilbink, 2012). Formal judicial independence was in place by the 1930s and prior to the coup in 1973 Chile had enjoyed decades of robust party competition and regular party alternation in power. Nevertheless, the Constitution of 1980 confirmed the absolute independence of the judiciary from other powers, and the selection process and the correct combination of check and balances the judges’ political independence (Navia, Mungiu-Pippidi and Martini, 2017).

The results from the indicators cited above can give us an overall view of the situation in the country regarding corruption and control of corruption. Even if current trends show a deterioration of the country position in different corruption indices, it is still possible to say that in Chile, in general terms, corruption continues to be exception rather than the norm. This means that conditions regarding the rule of law, formal institutions, and competition could allow tools and measures based in the principal-agent to be effective, if other conditions are also present. Even though no study about the specific prevalence of corruption at the municipal level is available, there are no reasons to believe that the diagnosis could be significantly different from the rest of Chilean institutions.

For the purpose of this research, I will use a particular formulation of the principal-agent model, specifically Mungiu-Pippidi’s equilibrium model. This approach expands a previous model proposed by Klitgaard (2000), indicating that a balanced anticorruption formula needs to address both resources and costs of corruption (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2010):

$$\textit{Corruption} = \textit{Resources (Power discretion + Material Resources)} - \textit{Constraints (Legal + Normative)}$$

The idea behind this formula corruption is an equilibrium between resources and constraints. For resources we can understand power discretion, such as monopoly of power or privileged access to influence and decision, plus material resources, such as public budget, natural resources, state assets or public jobs. For constraints, we can understand, on the one hand, legal constraints, particularly an autonomous and effective judiciary, and on the other, normative constraints, such as societal norms that effectively sanction departures from ethical universalism through public opinion, media, civil society and voters (Ibid).

In the following section I will build on this model to propose evaluation criteria that could be employed to select between several options regarding the process of financial decentralization of the Chilean local government level. As it is described below, the current process of decentralization implies assessing different organizational schemes and financial competences distributions that can affect the equilibrium between the different components of the selected explanatory model of corruption.

Problem statement and methodology

The Chilean government has made decentralization a priority since the late 2000's (OECD, 2017). In this context, during the government of Michele Bachelet, important steps were taken in 2009 and onwards with the definition of a Decentralization Agenda and the creation of a Presidential Advisory Commission for Decentralization. Moreover, a political consensus exists in the country about the need to advance in a decentralization process that reverts at some degree the significant political and administrative centralization that characterizes the Chilean State.

Given that any important modification of the distribution of competences between level of governments will likely affect the balance between resources and constraints as described in Mungiu Pippidi's model, especially if this redistribution has a financial nature, an evaluation of the different schemes acquires relevance. The question is, then, what kind of decentralization scheme has the capacity to maintain an adequate balance between resources and constraints, in such a way that, if a larger financial autonomy to local government (municipalities) is granted, it could be adequately compensated with different types of accountability and transparency mechanisms.

This paper will take the form of a prescriptive policy analysis (Patton et al, 2016). Following Bardach's policy analysis guide (2005), it first presents evidence about the current state of the Chilean municipal model and its consequences regarding the balance between resources and constraints for corruption. It also proposes several alternatives for fiscal decentralization schemes and evaluates them through an assessment of its effect on the components of the equilibrium model. Based on this evaluation, it puts forward several recommendations for the Chilean fiscal decentralization model for municipalities. A Municipal Transparency Index (MTI) is proposed, as way of distinguishing between municipalities with regard to their performance on different indicators that measure the timely provision of available and accessible public information.

The analysis is based on primary qualitative sources and secondary quantitative data. Primary sources are interviews conducted with representatives from the Chilean Association of Municipalities, the Council for Transparency, the Undersecretary of Regional Development (SUBDERE), PNUD's Office in Chile and the General Comptroller's Office (GCO).

For the construction of the MTI indicators the paper uses the three different data sources. First, the GCO's Observatorio del Sector Municipal. It provides, among other information, updated data about the municipalities' compliance with their accounting obligations. Municipalities are legally required to send monthly budgetary and accounting reports to the GCO's. The observatory tracks if these reports were delivered (on time). Second, the Council for Transparency annual report on municipal compliance with their active transparency obligations. The 2008 Transparency Law requires municipalities to keep permanently available to the public, through their websites, information about their budget, expenses, and tenders, among other sensitive data. From 2012 to 2018 the Council for Transparency implemented a general monitoring of these obligations and published an annual ranking of municipalities.³ Finally, the SUBDERE's National System of Municipal Information (SINIM). Among other services, its municipal data platform provides annual reports on municipalities' budget execution. It also informs if municipalities did not deliver all or some of their annual budgetary reports.

The index calculation is done by a weighted aggregation of three different subindices. The first is built by the author and portrays the compliance of municipal governments with their accounting obligations regarding the GCO's, particularly the delivery on time of monthly budgetary and accounting

³ This ranking was discontinued in 2019, as the Council changed its methodology to a more focalized monitoring of municipalities.

reports. The second is a composite of two different rankings provided by the Council for Transparency, assessing separately the compliance of municipalities and municipal corporations with their active transparency obligations. When the municipality does not count with a municipal corporation, then this indicator is only composed by the score granted by the Council for Transparency in the first ranking. The last one is also built by the author and measures the degree of compliance of municipalities with their obligation to provide the SINIM with their annual budgetary reports. All data corresponds to the year 2018.

First indicator: timely delivery of budgetary and accounting reports to the GCO's.

Chilean regulation obliges municipalities to deliver seven reports per month along the calendar year, plus five reports about the opening and closing of this time-lapse. As a result of consultations with experts, in this subindex the former is assigned a weight of 70% and the latter of 30%. Each weight is pondered against a percentage of the total of reports complied for each of these obligations.

$$X_{i,t} = \left(\left[(0.70) * \frac{Y_{i,t}}{84} \right] + \left[(0.30) * \frac{Z_{i,t}}{5} \right] \right) \times 100$$

Where $X_{i,t}$ is the local transparency subindex for municipality i , $Y_{i,t}$ is the total of reports the municipality i delivered in a span of 12 months, and $Z_{i,t}$ is the amount of reports the municipality i delivered at the beginning and end of the year. In all cases, t represents time. In this particular scenario, all the reports considered the time (t) as 2018. Finally, for terms of comparability, the subindex is multiplied by 100. The subindex range is 0 to 100, where 0 means total noncompliance and 100 total compliance of the municipality i for time t .

Second indicator: score in the Council of Transparency 2018's active transparency ranking.

As aforementioned, this subindex consists of two different estimations. The first is the score granted by the Council of Transparency to the municipality in its 2018's active transparency ranking, and the second, is the score granted to the municipality's corporation in the same ranking, in the case this corporation exists. These estimations are named here as A_i and B_i .

In both cases it is provided by Council for Transparency and, according to their methodology, it has a range from 0 to 100, 0 meaning complete noncompliance and 100 total compliance. Considering these two estimations, the subindex $U_{i,t}$ is assessed by the formula below, where i stands for the municipality, and t for the time. The value of $U_{i,t}$ ranges from 0 to 100.

$$U_{it} = \begin{cases} \frac{A_{i,t} + B_{i,t}}{2}, & \text{where there are local corporations} \\ A_{i,t}, & \text{where there are no local corporations} \end{cases}$$

Third indicator: delivery of annual budgetary information to the SINIM.

The last indicator informs the municipalities' degree of compliance with their obligations to provide the SINIM with their annual budgetary information. A_i considers that the total of items that should be delivered in a year are 114. $J_{i,t}$ denotes the number of items delivered by the municipality i on year t . The range is 0 to 100, in which 0 denotes total noncompliance and 100 total compliance.

$$A_{i,t} = \left[\frac{J_{i,t}}{114} \right] \times 100$$

Municipal Transparency Index (MTI).

Considering the subindices $X_{i,t}$, $H_{i,t}$, and $U_{i,t}$ as explained above and derivative with consultations with experts, the weightings for each are 45%, 45%, and 10% accordingly. This is pictured in the next formula, where i stands for the municipality, and t for the time. The value of $T_{i,t}$ ranges from 0 to 100 where 0 means total transparency by the municipality government, and 100 total opacity by the same.

$$T_{i,t} = [(0.45) * X_{i,t}] + [(0.45) * H_{i,t}] + [(0.10) * U_{i,t}]$$

Assessment of local governments in Chile

Chile is considered a unitary country. This means, in opposition to a federal state, a country governed by a single power in which the central government is ultimately supreme, in such a way that citizens are subject to the same single power throughout the national territory (OECD, 2019a). Moreover, Chile belongs to the group of OECD countries with two layers of subnational governments (OECD, 2017). At the regional level, government is currently politically decentralized and functionally deconcentrated. After the approval of Laws 21.073 and 21.074 in 2018, regional governments (GORE) are conformed by a regional governor, its main authority, and a regional council (CORE), both democratically elected. Under this layer, the local government in Chile is formed by municipalities. They are autonomous corporations of public law whose purpose is to satisfy the needs of the local community and ensure its participation in the economic, social, and cultural progress of their respective jurisdictional territories ('comunas')⁴. The Chilean municipal model presents several important specificities.

First, Chilean municipalities have a fairly complex array of attributions composed of exclusive and non-exclusive (shared) functions. Among the exclusive functions the most important are the promotion of local and development planning and the provision of services such as waste collection, water, and the administration of public spaces. With regard to the non-exclusive functions, municipalities share with the central government the responsibility over primary and secondary education and public basic health, but also road management, employment, environment, social housing, public transport, and social inclusion (OECD, 2017; Fernandez, 2013). This complexity has as consequence to make it very difficult for the population to hold local authorities accountable for the quality and the outcomes of the programs and services provided, as its responsibility is shared in many cases with the central government (Bernstein & Inostroza, 2009). Additionally, as education and health services count each with a different and separated municipal budget (amounting in total to 49% of the municipal expenditure), run by specific administrative departments, the result is an overly intricate system in terms of accountability and management (OECD, 2017).

Second, legislation allocates uniform statutory competences to municipalities, without taking into consideration size, population and other kinds of specificities that define the very heterogenous territorial, social, and economic reality of the country (Ibid). As noticed by the OECD, the delivery of a uniform set of public services seems unrealistic, if not impossible, when taking into consideration the huge disparities across municipalities in terms of needs and capacity (2013).

Third, a fairly limited financial autonomy given to municipalities; a historical remnant of a long tradition of strong centralization (OECD, 2017). Even though a "decentralization" process was intended during the Pinochet regime (1973-1990), in which responsibilities in educational and health services were granted to municipalities, shared with the national level, in practical terms this implied only the

⁴ Municipalities are regulated in the Organic Municipal Constitutional Law, Law No. 18.695 (LOCM).

deconcentration of certain functions. If we add this to a design that also aimed to reduce the size of the state through the privatization of public services, at national and local levels, municipalities became more “service delivery agents” than “local governments” (OECD, 2017; Fernandez, 2013). This can also be traced to the constitutional and legal regulation of Municipalities. The Constitution grants the municipalities only the local administration of the communes, not its government. This means that, at the subnational level, decision-making power, a proper feature of government, is rather allocated at the regional tier, in the Regional Governments, as stated in the Constitutional Organic Law on Regional Government and Regional Administration, Law No. 19.175 (Fernandez, 2013). In this sense, it does not surprise that Chile has one of the lowest levels of fiscal decentralization by subnational expenditure and tax revenue in the OECD (OECD, 2018)⁵.

Nevertheless, municipalities form the basic unit of the administrative structure in Chile. This means that a series of own and shared very significant attributions are allocated within the local government. These attributions are accompanied by a rather complex decision making and financial structure. In the next subsection I will analyze this structure from the point of view of the balance between resources and constraints, with the objective of providing a base for a further evaluation of decentralization schemes. Regarding resources, I will analyze the power discretion granted to authorities within the municipal structure, and the different types of means that they have at their disposal. In relation to constraints, the evaluation will encompass the monitoring and accountability framework in force, and also normative constraints, particularly related to civil society and voters.

An equilibrium assessment of municipalities

Power discretion. The two most important actors in the Chilean municipal structure are the mayor and the Municipal Council. Even though the mayor is the municipality’s highest authority, the head of its internal administration and its most important public figure, it shares a significant part of its attribution with the Council, the municipal co-legislative and supervisory body. In this sense, the mayor requires the approval of the Council for subjects as important as the definition of the municipal development plan, the annual municipal budget, the health and education budget, and the definition of the human resources, concessions, permits and tenders municipal policies (article 65 LOCM). Moreover, every year the mayor is required to inform the Council about the budget implementation and balance, municipal investments, administrative and judicial inquiries, and contracts under implementation, among others sensitive issues. The role of the Municipal Council is then critical for the limitation of the mayor’s discretion (P. Olguin, personal communication, April 1, 2022; F. Sanchez personal communication, April 14, 2022), and its supervisory attributions have been relevant in uncovering recent corruption cases at the local level.

Nevertheless, this internal accountability framework, some significant shortcomings are still present regarding check and balances within the municipal structure. Two are the most salient: the operation of municipal corporations and the granting of building permits.

Municipal corporations are a distinctive feature of the Chilean municipal framework. Created during Pinochet’s regime in 1980 (Decree No. 1-3.063) and then recognized by the LOCM, they are private non-profit entities that can be created by the mayor with the objective of administering more efficiently one or several services under municipalities’ competence (most prominently health and education services that were deconcentrated to the municipal level during Pinochet’s government).

⁵ This evaluation is done by calculating the spending decentralization as % of GDP and % of total public expenditure and tax revenue decentralization as % of GDP and % of total public tax revenue.

The legal framework of municipal corporation grants wide discretionary powers to the mayor (Observatorio Fiscal, 2017). First, the mayor serves as the corporation's chairman of the board of directors, with extensive attributions, particularly when it comes to human resources. Second, as municipal corporation are private entities, employment within them is not regulated by the public administration legislation, but by civil labor law. Third, as municipal corporation are not formally part of the municipalities' structure, their balances are not consolidated with the municipality's budget, which limits the internal municipal supervision and the action of the General Comptroller's Office (GCO). Fourth, municipal corporations manage a very large budget, with corporations, in average, having a budget that doubles their respective municipalities' (Council for Transparency, 2016).

This framework has been under heavy criticism for several years. For once, it provides the main municipal authority with an important discretionary power to hire, pay salaries and overtime to personnel, without being subjected to the controls and limitations of the regular municipal hiring regulation. Some severe budgetary issues have also emerged in corporations working for the largest municipalities in the country, with corporations affected by critical budgetary deficits in key aspects of municipal services (Observatorio Fiscal, 2017). This deficit is partially due to the massive debt that some municipal corporations carry for several years without any effective measure being taken, with the subsequent increase of the debt due to interests and penalties (Ibid).

Another critical aspect regarding power discretion in municipalities are building permits. In this case, issues about the use of discretionary power do not arise regarding the mayor, but the Director of the Department of Public Works (hereinafter the Works Director). The Works Director is responsible, among other functions, for the issuing of building permits. This is a complex and technical process, which involves different types and level of regulations. Moreover, the Works Director benefits from an important discretion when making its decision, as it is only limited by the Municipality Regulatory Plan, an instrument that provides the Works Director with a wide space for decision making. It is relevant to notice that even if the Works Director can be audited in its decisions by the mayor and the Municipal Council, critically these organs do not have the authority to remove it from office. This decision can only be made by the GCO when the Ministry of Housing and Urbanism has previously initiated a summary proceeding against the Work Director, which is a process that rarely takes place. On the other hand, both organisms can also audit the decisions about construction permits made by the Works Director, but this is only one their many functions, and they generally get involved only in the case of large projects or when their intervention is demanded by some interested party.

Then, comes to no surprise that the current regulation and functions of the Work Director has also been the object of intense debate. Some important corruption allegations related to the issuing of building permits benefiting large real estate companies have come to the public light and calls for the modification of its role are periodically made, sponsored especially by civil society organizations.

Resources. On the side of resources, as noticed before, Chile's centralized governance model is characterized by its rigid municipal regulatory and budgetary arrangements and its reduced financial maneuver for municipalities (OECD, 2017)⁶. Chilean subnational public revenue as a percentage of total public revenue is among the weakest in the OECD, as it represents only 14% of the public revenue (and 3.2% of the GDP), which contrasts with the average 42.3% in the OECD (and of 16% the GDP). This is

⁶ As the OECD points it, in very graphic terms, "Chile has opted for the mix of two models: on the one hand, an economic model that trusts markets mechanisms to distribute resources and that tends to limit public intervention; on the other hand, a political-administrative structure based on a strong centralization viewed as a way to maintain stability and unity" (2017: 133).

explained by the little autonomy that municipalities have in determining their revenues. Most of them come from the co-participation on taxes set by law for the entire national territory and at the exclusive initiative of the President of the Republic, such as the territorial tax (Horst, 2009). This lack of autonomy is also explained by the highly restrictive regulation regarding access to credit to finance local budgets, as municipalities are not allowed to borrow funds according to the Constitution and the LOCM (OECD, 2017).

In return, in a national context characterized by a very low overall public expenditure, this expenditure is even lower at the local level. According to the OECD, the Chilean Municipal spending per capita stood, at the year 2014, at USD 648, which was nearly 10 times less than OECD average. On the other hand, local investment, as a share of public investment, is also very low, representing only 12% of the total public spending, against the 59% OECD average (2016).

As an overall assessment, it is possible then to conclude that municipal authorities, in general terms, have a fairly reduced number of resources to their disposition. If we add to this that the totality of grants transferred from the central government have a conditional nature (Horst, 2009), then the public funds and assets that potentially could be affected by acts of corruption are rather limited (especially if they are compared to the resources that are administrated by the central government).

There are two very relevant exceptions. First, as it was indicated above, the possibility for the mayor of creating and administrating municipal corporations provides it with the capacity to decide on the creation and management of publicly funded jobs. Public jobs are a relevant source of resources and, as we have seen, the very loose regulation of municipal corporations implies that the mayor has access to an important pool of them with very few restrictions. Second, there are certain peculiarities of some municipalities that make them different in term of resources. As municipalities oversee community services, large communes distribute important funds when it comes to the procurement of community services such as waste collection or public lighting. It has been in relation to this aspect that some important alleged cases of corruption have been disclosed. Even though the Country Procurement Assessment Report (CPAR) from 2008, that evaluated the Chilean National System of Public Procurement and Contracting (Chilecompra), qualified the risk in procurement in the country as low (Inter-American Development Bank, 2008), it is important to notice that this system is not mandatory for the municipal level.

Legal Constraints. On the side of the legal constraints, we can distinguish between internal and external monitoring and accountability mechanisms. Internal mechanisms are in charge of the Municipal Council and the municipal Control Unit. As we have seen before, the Municipal council participates in the approval of the annual municipal budget, the health and education budget, and the definition of the human resources, concessions, permits and tenders municipal policies, among other subjects. The mayor is also required to inform the Council about the budgetary and liability issues. Moreover, since 1999 the Council can contract an external auditor to revise the accounts every two years, but this option is not often used (Valenzuela, 2008). The role of the Control Unit is to collaborate with the Council in its oversight functions. It is in charge of monitoring the municipal financial and budget execution, to perform an operational internal audit to control the legality of the municipality's actions and to inform the Council about any illegal activity attributed to the mayor (article 29 LOCM).

Regardless of the relevance of this control and audit framework, some important shortcomings have been diagnosed. In relation to the role of the Control Units, a report issued by the GCO on 2010 found important differences between municipalities and concluded that 60% of them did not fully comply with the minimum requirements and did not have the needed technical capacity to perform their duties (OECD, 2017). Among the deficits, the GCO found that 75% of municipalities did not have

a regulation chief auditor, 65% did not have internal operational audits, and that, overall, the Control Units lacked professionals adequately trained in IT systems and in financial, legal, and budget control (Ibid).

The external audit and control framework in Chile is formed by a system that connects the work of multiple institutions in charge of confronting corruption (GCO, 2020). For municipalities, four organisms are the most relevant: the GCO, the Council for Transparency, the Office of the Attorney General and the judicial system. I will focus here on the first two.

The GCO is an autonomous body controlling the legal aspects, management, preaudit, and post-audit functions of all the activities of the centralized and decentralized civil service. Municipalities must keep municipal accounts in accordance with the national accounting standards and with the instructions issued by the GCO and must adhere to the norms on the financial administration of the State (Fernández, 2013). In the case municipalities, the GCO exercises its functions mainly through audit actions that originate from its own planning or on the occasion of the submission of citizen complaints, claims or express requests from petitioners, such as parliamentarians (Ibid).

In this sense, it is important to notice that, beside particular audits performed under circumstances such as submissions or complaints, the GCO has a limited capacity to implement in depth periodic financial audits (OECD, 2017). Despite the fact that there is no available independent technical evaluation of the role of GCO in Chile (Waissbluth & von Wolfersdorff, 2018)⁷, it seems to exist an agreement between experts and government officials about the necessity to strengthen its preventive and audit capacities with regard to the operation of municipalities (P. Olguin, personal communication, April 1, 2022). The control that the GCO is capable to exercise over the local administration tends to have a formal nature. It has an emphasis on administrative compliance and lacks the means for comprehensive financial and technical audits that could provide certainty about the quality of the accounting data (Ibid).

A similar situation affects the Council for Transparency, the institution in charge of ensuring proper compliance with the Law of Transparency and auditing compliance with the rules of access to information (Law 20.285)⁸. The Council for Transparency controls procedures of active transparency – the compulsory publication of specific organizational and operational information –, and passive transparency – the provision of information when this has been requested by a member of the public in cases that is legally obligatory. Municipalities show uneven compliance with the law and, in general terms, have a lower level of compliance than the central administration, even though targeted work has been done on them (Espacio Publico et al, 2018). On the other hand, the Council of Transparency has the competence to control that the requested information is provided by municipalities but lacks the legal and material capabilities to monitor the quality and veracity of the information (D. Moreno, personal communication, April 14, 2022), which adds to the low levels of technological development in some municipalities preventing the efficient implementation of transparency platforms (Ibid).

⁷ Nevertheless, a recent survey conducted by the General Comptroller's Office shows a significant support of its work among the population (2020), and it is generally seen as an important and trustworthy pillar of the Chilean State (LyD, 2019).

⁸ The article 5 of Law 20.285 that creates the Council for Transparency states: "By virtue of the principle of transparency of the civil service, the acts and resolutions of the State and resolutions of the organs of the State Administration, their foundations, the documents that support or complement them, their grounds, the documents that support or complement them directly and essentially, and the procedures used for their dictation, are public, except for the cases established by this law and those provided for in other laws of qualified quorum".

Normative Constraints. The Chilean population demonstrates in general a low tolerance to acts of corruption. In a recent survey conducted by the Council for Transparency (2020) respondents were asked how acceptable do you think it is to give money/gift or do a favor to an official or manager of a public institution? With 84% of the respondents answering that is never acceptable. This goes hand in hand with the very critical view that Chileans have regarding probity in the public sector, particularly after a series of corruption scandals that have severely damaged public confidence in public institutions since the year 2000.

On the other hand, Chile benefits from a general respect and guarantee of free speech and media. In the Freedom in the World Survey version 2020 (Freedom House, 2020), Chile scores 15 out of 16 in the indicator of freedom of expression and belief, and 4 out of 4 in free and independent media. Moreover, in the World Press Freedom Index, a survey targeted at media professionals, lawyers and sociologists covering topics such as pluralism, media independence and abuses, Chile scores 27.89 and is ranked 54 out of 180 countries⁹. In this sense, even though the country faces some issues of media concentration, a strong independent media has been able to develop in the country, particularly after the recovery of democracy and the irruption of digital platforms. Digital media has been responsible, for instance, for in depth investigations covering corruptions in different public institutions, including municipalities.

Policy options for accountable fiscal municipal decentralization and recommendations

Taking into consideration the current balance between resources and constraints at the municipal level, several policy alternatives can be discussed with the goal of proposing an arrangement that, on the one hand, allows the Chilean State to advance in a process of local fiscal decentralization, and on the other, guarantees adequate control and accountability mechanisms. Moreover, two different models of decentralization can be proposed, distinguished by the homogeneity or heterogeneity of fiscal decentralization of local governments: symmetric decentralization, by which the whole subnational government level receives the same degree of fiscal autonomy, without distinctions, and asymmetric decentralization, by which different fiscal autonomy arrangements at the subnational level are implemented, depending on a defined criterion that allows to make distinctions among local governments (OECD, 2019a).

Features of symmetric and asymmetric fiscal municipal decentralization for Chilean municipalities

Several proposals have been made regarding the mechanisms to advance to a larger degree of fiscal autonomy for municipalities in Chile. As we have seen, the current legislation imposes a rigid and fragmented grant system, limited returns on tax revenue and restricted alternative sources of income, which results in Chile's local government having one of the weakest subnational public revenues in the OECD.

A symmetric measure of fiscal decentralization could imply the implementation of one or more of the following policies, applicable for all municipalities in the country:

- Shifting from earmarked to general purpose grants, increasing municipal discretion in intergovernmental transfers (and tying them to a results-based regulation instead of being steered to a specific use) (OECD, 2013; 2017).
- Allowing municipalities to determine the value of the land tax rate within the commune, as well as to define its exemptions (Horst, 2009). A second alternative regarding the land tax is

⁹ Countries are given scores ranging from 0 – best possible score, to 10 – worst possible score.

the implementation of a national government subsidy of land tax's exemptions when they affect particularly vulnerable municipalities, compensating them for the lost of revenue (Bernstein & Inostroza, 2009). This measure could encompass an autonomy enhancing mechanism if the subsidy received by municipalities is not earmarked or conditioned.

- Providing municipalities with greater and effective autonomy in relation to commercial patents, and the creation of tariffs and user fees (Horst, 2009). As noted by the OECD, "tariff and user fees are widely seen as the most appropriate source of revenues for metropolitan areas to finance the operation and maintenance expenses of infrastructure (e.g. parking fees, transport fees, fees on other public services including waste, water, energy) (2017: 188).
- Expanding municipalities' borrowing capacities, by loosening the current regulation that inhibits municipalities access to credit (OECD, 2017).
- Loosening restrictions on donations to municipalities (Bernstein & Inostroza, 2009).

An important risk of moving forward with a uniform fiscal decentralization process is the very different results that the process could produce across municipalities. As we have seen, Chilean municipalities present at this date significant differences in their operational and service provision capacities, which also applies to the quality of their budgetary monitoring and accountability mechanisms. An increase of fiscal autonomy that do not take into consideration these different capacities could have several unintended effects. On the one hand, an underutilization by poorer municipalities of revenue diversification mechanisms that require a proactive local government and adequate professional capacities to be exploited, such as the creation and management of tariff and users' fees and, most importantly, the taking and management of loans. On the other hand, municipalities without proper control mechanisms, for instance because of limited professional capacities in bodies such as the Municipal Council and the Control Unit, could see increasing opportunities for embezzlement and clientelism, as a result of new accesses to resources not being matched by stronger or diversified constraints.

At this point is important to remember that one of the main characteristics of the Chilean local government level is the significant differences that exists between municipalities. This reality contrasts with the prevalence of the symmetry principle, by which unitarian countries, such as Chile, have tried to enhance equity and integration of different parts of the country (OECD, 2019a). As the OECD has noticed, "[a]n analysis of individual municipal situations underscores their heterogeneity and dispersion, as well as the diversity of financial expenditure practices at the local level, which has been masked by a uniform perception of the functioning of the municipal system" (2017). As a consequence, a symmetric policy of decentralization could result in similar shortcomings seen in other reform process by means of assuming an inexistant uniformity in the capacity and operation of municipalities.

Some of these risks could be balanced by an incremental process that addresses the challenges just described. In this sense, an alternative that takes into consideration the differences between local governments is asymmetric decentralization. The implementation of a process of asymmetric fiscal local decentralization implies grating differential spending assignments, revenues autonomies, treatment in the transfer system or fiscal rules depending in criteria such as capacities, population, access to public services, budget, or performance (OECD, 2019a). Asymmetric arrangements are increasing, especially in unitary countries, based on motives such as metropolitan governance arrangements, asymmetric administrative decentralization, or the allocation of responsibilities to regions with greater capacity (Ibid).

Asymmetric decentralization has several advantages. Benefits are a better targeting of institutional and financial frameworks to local capacities, and the creation of conditions for

experimentation, learning-by-doing and innovation in policy making (Ibid). Moreover, asymmetric decentralization brings the possibility to tailor new resources and functions to the needs and capacities of subnational governments. Its incrementalism opens the door for a design that makes the process of implementation more manageable, also allowing a more precise assessment of its impact. This assessment can allow to prematurely detect deficiencies in the design and implementation, permitting further steps to be supported by evidence gathered during the process.

Aspects of the implementation of an asymmetric fiscal municipal decentralization in Chile

A measure of asymmetric fiscal municipal decentralization in Chile implies the differential allocation of greater financial autonomy to municipalities. increasing municipal discretion in intergovernmental transfers, providing municipalities with greater and effective autonomy regarding to land tax, patents, tariff as well as user fees, and expanding municipalities' borrowing capacities. The implementation of a such a measure requires the definition of, at least, two important aspects: the particular criteria that will define the allocation of these resources and the order by which municipalities should be selected to participate of the process.

Criteria for the allocation of new attributions. With regard to the first issue, it has to be taken into consideration that the decentralization mechanisms described above imply drastically expanding the financial capacity of municipalities, as they lose restrictions in the most important sources of income for local governments. For this reason, and without prejudging the adequacy of additional conditions, a particularly relevant requirement for the allocation of these attributions should be the municipal capacity to guarantee a fair and transparent administration of new, or less rigid, sources of revenue.

To this matter, several conditions can be established, specifically regarding the key aspects that have been highlighted as potential sources of mismanagement or lack of transparency in the municipal administration. The non-exhaustive list of proposed conditions that follows is built upon a series of diagnosis and recommendations made by different entities.

A first sensitive point is the Control Units' limited capability to perform an adequate financial and legal control, as many of them lack professionals trained in critical audit aspects. This was one of the key points highlighted by the Presidential Anticorruption Advisory Board created in 2015 by Michelle Bachelet. The Advisory Board proposed a process of professionalization of relevant functions within municipalities, included the Control Unit, by the implementation of a professional accreditation system consisting of a combination of national and local skills and knowledge exams (2015). A condition for the granting of greater fiscal autonomy should be then a certification issued by the GCO, linked to the proposed professional accreditation system, based on national and local exam required for sensible functions within the municipality, included the Control Unit.

The Advisory Board has also made recommendations regarding the heads of relevant municipal units, proposing for them to be selected by public competition of antecedents and opposition, with a similar orientation that the Chilean Senior Public Management System (SPMS). An additional recommendation has been made with regard to the Works Director, but in its case directly recommending its selection by the SPMS and defining its immobility by a fixed period of time (Ibid). A second condition linked to this assessment should be, therefore, the selection of heads of relevant units by public competition of antecedents and opposition, and the selection of the director of the Control Unit by the SPMS.

Another relevant recommendation has been the progressive reintegration to the municipal structure of activities currently performed by municipal corporations and the movement towards the

elimination of these bodies surrounding municipal framework. As stated by Observatorio Fiscal, two main obstacles exist today for the elimination of these corporations (2017). First, administrative and budgetary limitations would not allow many municipalities to absorb these functions, particularly with regard to health services. Second, it currently seems politically difficult to progress on the elimination of municipal corporations, if we consider that it is by means of their creation and administration that majors have found a way to circumvent at some degree legal and political constraints within municipalities (Ibid). Nevertheless, at least regarding the first obstacle, increased fiscal autonomy could actually help municipalities' absorption of services provided by municipal corporations, as a larger financial maneuver could create the conditions required for the process. A third condition, therefore, should be the absorption of services provided by municipal corporations, particularly as a requirement for receiving general purpose grants for health services. The national government can provide the technical, administrative, and financial assistance required by municipalities in this process.

Additional conditions can be a certification issued by the Council of Transparency linked to the compliance of municipalities with the Law of Transparency and rules of access to information, as well as the integration of the municipal procurement processes above certain amount to the National System of Public Procurement and Contracting (Chilecompra).

Prioritization of municipality types and process of implementation. The allocation of new resources and attributions decided on the basis of capacities can follow two different routes (OECD, 2019b). First, where there are large disparities between subnational governments, new spending or revenue powers can be first assigned to those more capable of handling the new responsibilities (Ibid). Alternatively, the smallest and weakest subnational governments could be the first to receive these new attributions. One of the main risks associated with asymmetric decentralization is its limitations when guaranteeing an equal treatment of subnational governments and citizens (OECD, 2019a), especially if the allocation of new resources and attributions is decided on the basis of capacities, without additional policies put in place in order to assist poorer or rural municipalities.

For these reasons, in the case of Chile, an asymmetric decentralization process beginning by the more vulnerable municipalities accompanied by an economic and technical support program delivered by the national government results is preferable. A process such as this, then, should be composed of, at least, the following elements:

- The formulation of typologies of municipalities in consideration to their capacities to receive new sources of revenues and expenditure attributions¹⁰.
- An assistance program organized, financed, and executed by the national government addressed to create the conditions for municipalities to bridge current gaps in budgetary management and control, as well with regard to transparency and accountability mechanisms. A central focus should be to enhance critical professional capabilities, by instance through compulsory and periodic training programs for all professionals working in sensitive areas such as the Control Unit. Other aspects that could be contemplated are the assistance for the compliance with active and passive transparency mechanisms, the reintegration in the municipal structure of services provided by municipal corporations, and the incorporation of

¹⁰ A categorization of municipalities with regard to factors such as development and urbanization already exists in the country under the management of the SUBDERE (2015; A. Barrientos, personal communication, April 4, 2022). Other models of categorization have also been proposed by experts and academics measuring aspects such as management, municipal expenditure in communication technologies, citizen participation and services provision (Matus et al, 2010).

municipal procurement processes above certain amount to the National System of Public Procurement and Contracting.

- A certification process assessing the existence of the minimal requirements for the allocation of these new attributions¹¹ with regard to pre-defined criteria that takes into consideration the aspects described before, among others. An intersectoral board could be in charge of the process of certification and the monitoring of aspects requiring improvement.

For the purposes of the first element, the formulation of typologies of municipalities, a tool such as the Municipal Transparency Index can be the basis for the selection of those municipalities that should be the focus of the decentralization policy.

Inspecting the seven municipalities with the best performance in terms of the timely provision of available and accessible public information it can be observed that four of them are located in the Metropolitan Region, while none, with the exception of Collipulli, has a population lower than 80,000 inhabitants (significantly higher than the average population for communes in Chile). In the top position of the ranking based on the MTI score, we find Vitacura, the wealthiest commune of the country, with a score almost 40 points higher than the national average (95.4 and 56.9, respectively).

On the opposite end, the list of the seven municipalities with the lowest MTI score is dominated by municipalities outside the Metropolitan Region (with the exception of Independencia). Four of them are located in the La Araucania and Bio-Bio regions, which count among the poorer and more undeveloped in the country (for instance, La Araucania population has an income that averages around 30% less than the rest of the country).

These results are consistent with the evaluation of experts and different organisms, in terms of the relevant differences that exists between municipalities' capacities. It is also indicative of the possible factors that influence municipalities' compliance with their legal obligations related to transparency and accountability. This information can help determine the route that the process of fiscal decentralization should follow, signaling those jurisdictions that would benefit from the national government's support in the strengthening of its transparency and accountability internal mechanisms. The latter, as a precondition for the allocation of new attributions and as way of counterbalance the risks posed by increasing resources not matched by appropriate controls and constraints.

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¹¹ The current SUBDERE's Municipal Management Strengthening System measures municipalities' management capacities and quality in a wide range of aspects, such as strategy, leadership, people competence, training, workplace safety and well-being, municipal revenues, municipal budget, material resources, user satisfaction, communication, and municipal services delivery processes (SUBDERE, 2015).

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